

**IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DISTANCE LEARNING
TECHNOLOGY IN THE SYSTEM OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT**

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Brief abstract: This article includes the basic principles, technology and efficiency of use of remote training for formation knowledge and skills of the students in process improvement of professional skill are examined.

Keywords: training systems, pedagogical research, distance learning systems, interdisciplinary connections.

Introduction

In the XXI century, the role of the teacher is improving. Nowadays, global changes, science and technology and the daily development of information and communication technologies require a teacher to have high skills, sharp will, psychological strength, deep knowledge and thinking.

Today, in the process of radical reform of the education system of the country, special attention is paid to strengthening the material and technical base of the system of professional development and ensuring its effective use, improving curricula and textbooks. At present, in the context of the widespread introduction of modern technologies in the system of professional development, the organization of the educational process on the basis of modern requirements and criteria, technical support of all departments of educational institutions, the use of the Internet.

At present, the basic didactic principles of education development in the system of professional development are also the basis for distance learning. Such technology of education is improved and supplemented with new conditions and criteria for a new learning environment. The organization of training in advanced training systems on the basis of modern technologies such as computers, software, multimedia electronic manuals, the Internet, electronic databases, distance learning must meet the following requirements:

- to organize classes on the basis of advanced achievements of science and modern technologies on the basis of modern laws of educational process and to provide optimal ratio of all didactic principles and rules;

- to create the necessary conditions for the thorough acquisition of knowledge by students, taking into account the interests, abilities and needs of students, as well as to establish interdisciplinary connections;
- relying on previously acquired knowledge and skills, as well as the level of development of students;
- motivation and activation of all-round development of the person of information technologies;
- increase the logic and emotionality of all stages of educational activities on the basis of information technology;
- effective use of information technology tools;

Forming the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities, rational ways of thinking and acting on the basis of information technology, creating the need to constantly enrich the existing knowledge and carefully design, plan, diagnose and predict each lesson.

The use of modern information and computer technology in the system of teacher training and retraining is carried out in the following areas:

- as an object of study of information and telecommunication technologies, i.e. students will have a general understanding and skills in new information technologies, their components and areas of use;
- information and telecommunication technologies as a means of teaching, i.e. on the basis of modern information and pedagogical technologies, knowledge is taught to students, and lectures, practical and laboratory classes are organized on the basis of modern computer software;
- as a means of managing the educational process, i.e. the creation of a system of information, analysis and forecasting to increase the effectiveness of all activities of the educational institution, including educational, spiritual, educational and research work taught.

Knowledge and skills on creation and implementation of modern information systems will be formed to increase the effectiveness of research and pedagogical research.

In the process of professional development and retraining of teachers, i.e. in lectures, practical, laboratory and seminar sessions, depending on the place of application of modern curricula, and the independent acquisition of knowledge by students, repetition of previous topics, The use of knowledge in the process of verification, control, provides an important basis for strengthening their knowledge and skills on the subject under study, as well as improving the learning process.

The use of distance learning technologies in the system of in-service training has specific pedagogical and psychological purposes, including:

- to teach students to make independent decisions in the implementation of a complex process, to express their views and opinions, as well as to form research activities;
- accelerate the learning process in all education systems;
- improving the perfection, productivity, quality and efficiency of the education sector in the implementation of the capabilities of information and communication technologies;
- deepening of science-communication in the use of information and communication technologies;
- development and implementation of distance learning systems based on the use of network technologies.

The implementation of the scientific principle of teaching in the process of distance learning implies that students learn scientific facts, concepts and laws, as well as theories in a particular subject. The principle of science requires students to develop research skills. This requires the widespread use of problem-based learning methods in the laboratory and in practice. Successful implementation of this principle in distance learning serves to ensure the fundamentality of the acquired knowledge.

Conclusion

Distance learning is a new form of teaching that differs from the forms of teaching that are separate and inseparable from production. It refers to new forms, methods, tools, organization, forms of communication between teacher and student, as well as student interaction. Also, different forms of such education will have their own purpose, based on social order, the content defined in the curriculum of the selected educational institution, as well as the organizational form and special means of teaching methods.

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